

Postcolonial Perspective in Salman Rushdie's *Shalimar the Clown*

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Abstract

*This Paper focuses on the postcolonial perspective in Salman Rushdie's *Shalimar the Clown* and especially focuses on the main character of the novel, *Shalimar*. The rapid explanation is used to emphasize the different postcolonial propensity in the fictional village *Pachigam*, in *Shalimar the Clown*. This village *Pachigam* is a place of hybridists, fluidity, and also a space marked by distinction. It is distinctive but not a smooth postcolonial space, one which Brennan ignores in his definition of post colonialism. The paper describes essentially about the vague relationship of the village *Pachigam*, a microcosm of Kashmir with the larger 'postcolonial', 'post-imperial' entities of India and Pakistan. The paper also analyses the women's sufferings, psychology and injustice in postcolonial India.*

Keywords: Verbal confrontations, neo-colonialism, conventions, border issues, revenge.

Salman Rushdie's *Shalimar the Clown* is a case of how the current postcolonial novel verbal confrontations fear mongering, the neo-colonialist procedures of post-war US outside strategy and the Indian military nearness in Kashmir and how India suffered from terrorism. It also extends premise of their argument about conventions and economic globalization, resurgent separatist and fanatic movements and its impact on every individual. *Shalimar, the Clown* across many hurdles of different periods of time and territories, challenges the empire's legacies, nationhood and emergent new empires.

Shalimar the Clown discusses the repressions and exclusions that the postcolonial state imposes on its border, exemplified in the continuing unannounced war between India and Pakistan over Kashmir. *Shalimar the Clown* routes postcolonial patterns by examining transnational fearer networks and their regional and international force on politics, cultures and religion. It is perceived how terrorism has affected the whole humankind with its hurtful results. Through the character of *Shalimar, the Clown*, the reader notices how exact revenge makes him fear based tyrant who later on turns into the motive for killing of individuals and afterward disguise turns into the reason for onslaught. Fear based oppression is a worldwide marvel which needs exceptional consideration. Hostile

to fear based tyrant activity is upheld by popular assessment. This has been the explanation behind the end, danger of psychological tyrant and also it promotes worldwide clashes. Patriotism gets to be distinctly forceful and it makes the general population intolerant of different group of people and nations. One has to understand that no men are alien and no nation is strange. In this way to control the psychological cruelty common understanding is likewise important between various societies and groups.

Salman Rushdie depicts the social conventions, cultural practices, and religious faiths, familial and familiar relationship, the reliable burden of traditional authority that has generated a rebellion against the organized forces of oppression and injustice to women. Through his novels, Salman Rushdie promotes the idea that women must try to come out of their suppressed roles. He has been successful in creating strong women protagonists who refuse to get crushed under the weight of their personal tragedies, and face life with great courage and strength.

The novel describes partly in a small village in the region of Kashmir. The village itself is imaginary and it is located in Srinagar. The book is divided into five parts, which are told through the eyes of the five main characters. The first section, set in present day Los Angeles, revolves around the life of India Ophuls, a beautiful documentary maker and the daughter of Max Ophuls, a former American ambassador to India and the later the US counterterrorism Chief.

A twenty four year old ambassador's daughter, India Ophuls sleeps badly through the warm, unsurprising nights. At times, she cries out in a language she does not speak. No men would stand in front of her while she sleeps. Her words would be science-fictional like Klingon, like a throat being cleared in a galaxy far, far away. Before her death, Boonyi has revealed the truth about her father who is an ambassador, to her daughter, India Ophuls. Her mother has been a Kashmiri, and is lost to her, like paradise, like Kashmir, in a time before memory. She trembles before her mother's absence and has waited without knowing she is waiting. After her father's death who was once a brilliant, cosmopolitan, Franco-American, "Like Liberty", often absent, irresistible father.

So, until her father's death, she was not an easy woman to sleep with, though she was a woman with whom men wanted to sleep. The pressure of men's desires was tiresome to her.

The pressure of her desires was for the most part unrelieved. (SC 4)

A few lovers she has taken are unsatisfactory and soon, she gives up serious consideration to her proposal of marriage. One day, the ambassador is slaughtered on her doorstep like a halal chicken dinner, bleeding to death from a deep neck that was caused by a single slash of the assassin's blade. India presents India Ophuls as a disciplined, groomed nuanced, inward, irreligious, understood and calm girl. In her behaviour she is not heated, but cool. The problematic child within her is sublimated into her spare-time pursuits, the weekly boxing sessions at Jimmy Fish's boxing club on Santa Monica and Vine. The arrow is her weapon of choice. India sees the desirous, old women flirting on the verandahs, the lurking spiteful old men.

The antique Russian super, Olaga Simeonovna, a bulbous denim-clad samovar of a woman, greets the ambassador and told the Ambassador that his daughter keeps waiting for him. She is known to all in the town as she is good at potato magic. A woman like her lives in between America and Astrakhan. She has been born a few miles east of the Volga River delta, within sight of the Caspian Sea. Then, the history of 20th century is shaped by her potato magic. She has told the old ladies and gentlemen that she can corner her wherever and whenever she could for India and now she is invited for the twenty-fourth birthday of Ambassador Max Ophuls's daughter. She is not ridiculous, and she never permits herself to sink into fantasy. She notices a driver waiting patiently nearby the elevator, holding the door and he tells his name as "Shalimar" when she asks.

Shalimar's English is not good, barely functional-even and he is unaware of that phrase. His eyes are blue; his skin colour is lighter than hers; his hair looks grey with a memory of fair. He

escorts her downstairs. India Ophuls's father asks her what she has wanted for her birthday. She has asked pornographic questions looking at the driver. She wants to see his smile. But he couldn't have understood the word and smiles without knowing what he is agreeing to. She too wants her mother. She asks her father to tell about her mother, to show her letters, photographs, to bring messages from the dead. She wants her lost story to be found.

The freedom that Boonyi chooses for herself is "false, a fantasy, an attraction to tempt her to sin, which she ... like Eve, is easily tempted and eagerly accepts the Ambassador's offer of a change ..." (Mathur 2007:92) In the poor village of Boonyi she finds the keenness for freedom, lured by which she symbolizing Kashmir, loses herself courting devastation.

"Rushdie expresses sadness for the ideal that has been lost in Kashmir and in so many parts of the Muslim world, the ideal of tolerance and secular pluralism" (Cowley 2005:27). This novel is the moving story of Noman, who called himself Shalimar the clown partly in the honour of his lady love, son of the village headman. He is a sweet innocent boy, "clown prince of the performing troupe" (SC 50), a young boy madly in love with Pandit Pyarelal Kaul's daughter, Bhoomi or Boonyi as she prefers to be called.

The Ambassador gifts a car to India Ophuls. "There is no room for three people in this rocket ship" (SC 12), She says aloud. She has appointed a handsome driver, Shalimar from Kashmir. She has felt the driver wanting to touch her in the elevator that is she feels herself transformed into an abstraction. She wants to be the kind of woman who could ask a driver, "who do you want to touch when you want to touch me ... we can have sex in elevators and never mention it.

Sex in transit Zones, in places like elevators that are between one place and the next, sex in cars... and the rest of the time, forget it, you're my father's employee" (SC 13).

The driver could not understand her language anyway; she really has no knowledge of the level of his language skills. This is the last day she and her father would ever spent together. She has her first subject for a documentary film and there is money enough to begin work. They eat hungrily in a High Canyon Lodge. Father and daughter are alike in their appetites, their high metabolic rates, their love of meat, and their slender high-toned bodies. She offers an invocation aloud to make his father smile. "This flesh whereof we eat is not their (ass) true flesh but the flesh of others like them, through whom their own lost forms may be conjured up and honoured" (SC 14).

India Ophuls talks about Shalimar to her father, the ambassador. She has pictured the other Shalimar, the great Mughal garden of Kashmir, descending in verdant liquid terraces to a shining lake that she has never seen. The name meant "abode of joy". She sets her jaw, "it still sounds like a candy bar to me." (SC 25) Khomdram Shyamsundram Singh writes:

The novelist has indeed designed a blot of sorts each for all the women characters, not with an ulterior motive to lend them an aura of being only flesh and blood, but to either demean or stigmatize them: Padma is like a plaything for Saleem; Reverend mother is conventional to a fault; Alia is vindictive; Emerald has no love for her sisters; Amina Sinai, Pia and Lila Sabarmati are tarred with the brush of infidelity; Elvyn and Brass Monkey embody both wildness and violence; Parvati's life ends on a very sordid note and the historical personality Indira Gandhi is depicted as a demon in the form of a woman. (Singh 55)

Max Ophuls is a bastard and she wished he is dead, but that is just her way of talking, she is an artist of passion, a hot-blooded woman, and everyone thinks how such a woman speak of a man who has proved himself unworthy of her love. She herself is incapable of murder; she is a woman of peace; her eyes are innocent and she has been paying attention to the confession that she could have saved a human life, even if it is only the life of a human worm like Max Ophuls.

Boonyi's presence is an indication by Salman Rushdie that Kashmir will not be lost; it will emerge from the darkness into the light of true freedom and hope for its entire people, a new

life. She symbolizes this new beginning in her realization and acceptance of her true identity and ultimately in her emerging victory by executing the hatred and violence of Shalimar. She was no longer a prisoner of fury when she lets her arrow find its mark. In the end of the novel, Salman Rushdie says, “She was not fire but ice” (SC 398).

Salman Rushdie has depicted the corrupted individual and terrorist during post colonialism in *Salimar the Clown*. The history of India and the entity are corrupted because of the sensitive feelings of a few characters like Boonyi, Salimar and India Ophuls. Kashmir becomes a place of hell and it is rotted by itself because of the people as represented by Salman Rushdie. The emergence of violence is delineated during postcolonial period.

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